

Table 3 List of the rodent species and morpho-functional indices used in analysis of locomotory characteristics. Measurements for *Calomyscus elburzensis* (Calomyscidae), *Apodemus witherbyi*, *Meriones persicus*, *Rattus norvegicus*, *Rhombomys opimus* (Muridae), and *Scarturus elater* (Dipodidae) are related to the present study, while data for the rest of species are extracted from Samuels & Van Valkenburgh (2008), including *Anomalurus pelii* (Anomaluridae), *Arvicola terrestris italicus* and *Nectomys squamipes* (Cricetidae), *Jaculus orientalis* and *Scarturus hotsoni* (Dipodidae), *Hystrix cristata* (Hystriidae), *Colomys goslingi* (Muridae), *Glaucmys sabrinus*, *Hylopetes nigripes*, *Paraxerus cepapi*, *Ratufa affinis*, *Sciurus niger* and *Spermophilus beecheyi* (Sciuridae), *Nannospalax leucodon*, *Rhizomys pruinosus* and *Spalax giganteus* (Spalacidae). Morphological indices are as follows: Shoulder moment index (SMI)= LPH/LH, Brachial index (BI)= LR/LH, Humeral robustness index (HRI)= HMLD/LH, Humeral epicondylar index (HEB)= WE/LH, Olecranon length index (OLI)= LO/(LU-LO), Ulnar robustness index (URI)= UMLD/(LU-LO), Manus proportions index (MANUS)= PPH/MC, Crural index (CI)= LT/LF, Gluteal index (GI)= FGT/LF, Femoral robustness index (FRI)= FAPD/LF, Femoral epicondylar index (FEI)= FEB/LF, Tibial robustness index (TRI)= TMLD/LT, Tibial spine index (TSI)= LPT/LT, Pes length index (PES)= LMT/LF, Intermembral index (IM)= (LH+LR)/(LF+LT). Abbreviations mentioned above and detailed descriptions of measurements are included in Table 1 and shown in Figure 14. Abbreviations for locomotion type (LT) are as follows: AE: Aerial, AR: Arboreal, FO: Fossorial, SA: Semi-aquatic, SF: Semi-fossorial, ST: Saltatorial, TE: Terrestrial.

ID no.	Species (Scientific name)	LT	SMI	BI	HRI	HEB	OLI	URI	MANUS	CI	GI	FRI	FEI [†]	TRI	TSI	PES	IM
1	Pel's scaly-tailed squirrel (<i>Anomalurus pelii</i>)	AE	0.326	0.922	0.060	0.148	0.100	0.028	0.925	1.042	0.048	0.056	0.124	0.043	0.380	0.228	0.813
2	Northern flying squirrel (<i>Glaucmys sabrinus</i>)	AE	0.318	1.129	0.064	0.172	0.091	0.016	0.905	1.173	0.072	0.058	0.142	0.045	0.311	0.379	0.843
3	Palawan flying squirrel (<i>Hylopetes nigripes</i>)	AE	0.361	1.052	0.066	0.182	0.103	0.025	0.846	1.127	0.075	0.064	0.145	0.048	0.316	0.329	0.790
4	Smith's bush squirrel	AR	0.422	0.930	0.090	0.263	0.159	0.047	0.760	1.163	0.101	0.081	0.197	0.064	0.349	0.438	0.725

	(<i>Paraxerus cepapi</i>)																
5	Pale giant squirrel (<i>Ratufa affinis</i>)	AR	0.399	0.824	0.079	0.247	0.160	0.039	0.839	1.023	0.088	0.077	0.189	0.060	0.390	0.397	0.780
6	Eastern fox squirrel (<i>Sciurus niger</i>)	AR	0.420	0.941	0.085	0.269	0.160	0.038	0.772	1.137	0.099	0.078	0.185	0.064	0.342	0.422	0.731
7	Brown rat (<i>Rattus norvegicus</i>)	TE	0.55	0.86	0.08	0.27	0.15	0.09	-	1.03	0.10	0.10	0.16	0.065	0.65	0.38	0.65
8	Persian jird (<i>Meriones persicus</i>)	TE	0.61	1.13	0.10	0.27	0.12	0.05	-	0.93	0.11	0.07	0.12	0.064	0.56	0.38	0.55
9	Steppe field mouse (<i>Apodemus witherbyi</i>)	TE	0.42	-	-	0.22	0.13	-	-	1.17	-	-	-	-	0.60	0.48	-
10	Goodwin's brush-tailed mouse (<i>Calomyscus elburzensis</i>)	TE	0.46	1.07	0.07	0.25	0.12	0.05	0.66	1.30	0.08	0.06	0.17	0.063	0.49	0.67	0.69
11	Small five-toed jerboa (<i>Scarturus elater</i>)	ST	0.46	1.17	0.11	0.32	-	-	0.73	1.40	0.08	0.08	-	0.059	0.35	0.91	0.67
12	Hotson's five-toed jerboa (<i>Scarturus hotsoni</i>) [†]	ST	0.466	1.239	0.093	0.292	0.156	0.036	0.688	1.561	0.109	0.072	0.155	0.049	0.246	1.108	0.367
13	Greater Egyptian	ST	0.459	1.242	0.101	0.333	0.159	0.046	0.626	10.601	0.109	0.076	0.177	0.054	0.234	1.201	0.358

	jerboa (<i>Jaculus orientalis</i>)																
14	Lesser blind mole rat (<i>Nannospalax leucodon</i>)	FO	0.633	0.829	0.118	0.343	0.536	0.094	0.617	1.010	0.166	0.104	0.274	0.075	0.514	0.285	0.870
15	Hoary bamboo rat (<i>Rhizomys pruinosus</i>)	FO	0.556	0.799	0.129	0.324	0.346	0.071	0.569	0.933	0.121	0.101	0.250	0.089	0.513	0.310	0.842
16	Giant blind mole rat (<i>Spalax giganteus</i>)	FO	0.640	0.736	0.126	0.284	0.587	0.108	0.569	1.021	0.138	0.102	0.246	0.082	0.507	0.217	0.859
17	Great gerbil (<i>Rhombomys opimus</i>)	SF	0.50	0.74	0.10	0.28	0.19	0.14	-	-	0.14	0.11	0.16	-	-	0.30	-
18	Crested porcupine (<i>Hystrix cristata</i>)	SF	0.577	0.768	0.103	0.317	0.308	0.091	0.456	1.000	0.159	0.109	0.284	0.097	0.386	0.296	0.870
19	California ground squirrel (<i>Spermophilus beecheyi</i>)	SF	0.431	0.901	0.096	0.266	0.181	0.049	0.639	1.035	0.102	0.085	0.200	0.081	0.372	0.393	0.770
20	Italian water vole (<i>Arvicola terrestris italicus</i>) [‡]	SA	0.504	0.940	0.089	0.246	0.213	0.057	0.635	1.121	0.104	0.078	0.202	0.074	0.434	0.390	0.790
21	African wading rat (<i>Colomys goslingi</i>)	SA	0.445	1.228	0.089	0.267	0.127	0.037	0.655	1.489	0.118	0.082	0.216	0.051	0.295	0.787	0.646
22	South American	SA	0.455	1.011	0.078	0.260	0.172	0.036	0.622	1.251	0.137	0.092	0.209	0.066	0.429	0.607	0.655

water rat
(*Nectomys*
squamipes)

[¶] *FEI* in this study is the same index to *FEB* which has been mentioned in Samuels & Van Valkenburgh (2008).

[†] Hotson's five-toed jerboa (*Scarturus hotsoni*) previously included in the genus *Allactaga* and later *Paralactaga*, which has recently been found to be a junior synonym of *Scarturus* (Michaux & Shenbrot, 2017).

[‡] Italian water vole (*Arvicola italicus*) was treated until recently as a synonym of *A. amphibius* (earlier of *A. terrestris*). Phylogenetic reconstructions using molecular markers retrieved *A. italicus* as a distinct species (Pardiñas et al., 2017).